

Urban Relief

Kick-off summary and detailed work plan

D1.1

Document Factsheet

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Project Partners

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Acronyms

EAB	External Advisory Board
COCD	Center for Design of Creative Thinking
GA	General Assembly
ODI	Open Data Institute
SC	Steering Committee
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal

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Project Summary

Urban ReLeaf will deliver citizen-powered data ecosystems to support cross-sectoral innovation and political agenda setting for climate change adaptation and green infrastructure planning in urban environments. At the heart of Urban ReLeaf’s action- and mission-oriented approach to innovation are public authorities, established communities and citizen groups in six pioneering Urban ReLeaf cities: Athens, Dundee, Utrecht, Cascais, Mannheim and Riga. Public sector innovation will be underpinned by co-creation efforts and inclusive citizen participation, cutting-edge technologies to support citizen observations, as well as robust and quality-assured workflows for the integration and visualization of the data in authoritative data streams and platforms. The solutions will be piloted through civic engagement campaigns with established volunteer communities, focusing on the inclusion of minority and marginalized groups. Urban ReLeaf will showcase the democratization of urban greenspace monitoring and the wider policy-making process for cities in pursuit of urban climate resilience. Ultimately, the Urban ReLeaf data ecosystem and associated governance models will deliver new, inclusive pathways for data-driven decision making in support of the European Green Deal and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) keeping cities resilient, livable, and accessible for all.

Executive Summary

This report summarizes the activities undertaken during the project kick-off workshop on January 25-27, 2023 in Laxenburg, Austria. In addition to the workshop program, key outcomes and a detailed project plan for the first year of the project are described.

1. Introduction

The Urban ReLeaf kick-off workshop was held at the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) in Laxenburg, Austria on January 25-27, 2023. All partner institutions were represented at this three-day hybrid event. The aim of the kickoff was to initiate the first steps towards the realization of the Urban ReLeaf action-oriented mission:

To advance citizen-powered science to be a central resource for inclusive urban green planning and policy in support of the European Green Deal and the SDG 11.7 target¹

The workshop, organized by the project coordinator IIASA, established an ambitious agenda that employed targeted breakout groups and working sessions to facilitate discussion around key topics (i.e. policy/stakeholder mapping and project values). In addition, the workshop aimed at relationship building between the partners, stimulating enthusiasm and inaugurating successful working partnerships. The following report outlines the activities carried out during the workshop and some of the major outcomes.

2. Urban ReLeaf consortium

The Urban ReLeaf consortium will be led by the Novel Data Ecosystems for Sustainability Research Group (NODES) at IIASA, which has considerable experience in managing past EU projects including the Horizon 2020 funded LandSense Citizen Observatory and the WeObserve project. The team is composed of 15 partner organizations from nine European countries (Figure 1). Among the partners, eight are research and development entities with extensive expertise spanning key domains including citizen science, civic technologies, participatory methods, innovative governance and earth observation for environmental monitoring (Table 1). The consortium benefits from established links to the WeObserve project, e.g., through the experiences and still engaged members of the four successful Communities of Practice, the networks created, and the valuable resources that were developed as part of this project including the WeObserve Roadmap. Additionally, at the heart of the team are seven city/provincial level partners representing the six Urban ReLeaf pilot locations: Athens, Dundee, Utrecht, Cascais, Mannheim, and Riga. These policy making entities are geographically spread across Europe but are all united in their needs to improve urban greening infrastructure and urban resilience to climate change as well as having the foresight and willingness to investigate the value and engagement of citizens for environmental monitoring and decision making. Many of these cities are also part of other progressive initiatives (e.g., Covenant of Mayors, European Bauhaus Initiative, the Green City Accord, etc.), which demonstrates their commitment to achieving successful Urban ReLeaf outcomes. Moreover, all these city partners are part of ICLEI's extensive urban network, where ICLEI will work with these partners to develop innovative governance models that facilitate the uptake of citizen observations in authoritative databases.

¹ By 2030, provide universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces, particularly for women and children, older persons and persons with disabilities

Figure 1. The Urban ReLeaf team at the kick-off workshop at IIASA, Laxenburg, Austria

Table 1: Urban ReLeaf project consortium

No.	Partner	Short Name	Country
1	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis	IIASA	Austria
2	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	VUB	Belgium
3	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems	ICCS	Greece
4	CIBOS Innovation Idiotiki Kefalaiouchiki Etaireia	CIBOS	Greece
5	ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH	ICLEI	Germany
6	University of Dundee	UNIVDUN	United Kingdom
7	Ethniko Asteroskopeio Athinon	NOA	Greece
8	Collecte Localisation Satellites	CLS	France
9	Dimos Athinaion Epicheirisi Michanografisis	DAEM	Greece
10	Dundee City Council	DCC	United Kingdom
11	Gemeente Utrecht	CITYUTR	The Netherlands
12	Provincie Utrecht	PROV UTR	The Netherlands
13	Empresa Municipal de Ambientede Cascais	EMAC	Portugal
14	Stadt Mannheim	MANN	Germany
15	Riga Planosanas Regions	RPR	Latvia

3. Workshop program and activities

The key objectives of the workshop included:

1. Create a common understanding of the Urban ReLeaf motivation, purpose and mission-oriented approach
2. Reinforce the project objectives underpinning the scientific and innovation agenda

3. Build strong and sustainable working partnerships
4. Co-define the scale and direction of the Urban ReLeaf city pilots
5. Generate a robust year 1 work plan, establishing responsibilities and timelines

To help achieve these workshop objectives, a series of interactive sessions/activities were organized (Table 2).

Table 2: Urban ReLeaf kick-off workshop session and activities

DAY 1 – JANUARY 25, 2023
Welcome & Introductions (IIASA) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project motivation • Mission-oriented approach • Workshop communication protocols
Work Package Overviews <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP1: Project management & coordination + WP7: Ethics (IIASA) • WP2: Stakeholder dialogue & inclusive citizen participation (VUB) • WP3: Bridge citizen-powered & authoritative data ecosystems (ICCS) • WP4: Mobilize participants & implement Urban ReLeaf pilots (IIASA) • WP5: Accelerate the uptake of citizen observations for decision-making (ICLEI) • WP6: Dissemination, exploitation & strategic communication (UNIVDUN)
Urban ReLeaf City Pilot Teasers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dundee: Citizen engagement for resilient Blue Green Infrastructure transitions (DCC) • Athens: Participatory tree registry and air quality monitoring (DAEM) • Utrecht: Mitigating heat stress through private greening & active community management (CITYUTR) • Cascais: Bioclimatic comfort analysis and resilience with Nature-based Solutions (EMAC) • Mannheim: Citizen engagement for building a tree registry and mitigating heat stress (MANN) • Riga: Adaptive community-based urban environment planning for the wellbeing of citizens (RPR)
DAY 2 – JANUARY 26, 2023
Welcome & Day 1 Recap (IIASA)
WP2+WP3 Workshops on Urban ReLeaf Pilots (VUB & ICCS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Breakout interactive sessions with pilot leads working on stakeholder, policy and data ecosystem mapping (D2.1, D2.2, D3.1)
Synthesis of Urban ReLeaf pilots <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reporting back from morning breakout sessions
WP6 Workshop on Urban ReLeaf core values and branding (UNIVDUN) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive session on project (visual) identity, comms strategy, storytelling, inclusive guidelines, etc. (D6.1, D6.2)
DAY 3 – JANUARY 27, 2023
Welcome & Day 2 Recap (IIASA)
Sister Project Presentations from HORIZON-CL6-2022-GOVERNANCE-01-08 call <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CitiObs - Enhancing Citizen Observatories for healthy, sustainable, resilient and inclusive cities (NILU) • GREENGAGE - Engaging citizens/mobilizing technology/delivering the green deal (AIT)
Urban ReLeaf Task List & Action Plan (IIASA) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Year 1 roadmap of tasks, responsibilities, deliverables and milestones
Urban ReLeaf Management and Coordination (IIASA) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on project meeting structure, General Assembly (GA), Steering Committee (SC), Microsoft Teams/Sharepoint, Reporting, External Advisory Board (EAB), Risk Management, Dissemination/Communications log, Ethics, Data Management Plan, etc.

4. Outcomes

The highlighted program and activities achieved a highly productive and successful start to the Urban ReLeaf initiatives. On Day 1, the WP leads (IIASA, VUB, ICCS, ICLEI and UNIVDUN) detailed sub-tasks for the first year and assigned partners' responsibilities and roles. Additionally, WP leads identified interdependencies and linkages across the six WPs (Figure 2), while flagging potential barriers and challenges. The Urban ReLeaf city pilot teasers from the local/provincial authorities (DCC, DAEM, CITYUTR, EMAC, MANN, RPR) helped to establish an initial common ground for co-designing the pilot activities. Partners presented the pilot scope/objectives and shared ongoing urban greening or planning initiatives within their cities. Particular attention was given to recognizing gaps and opportunities for citizen science to contribute to inclusive place and policy making solutions. During this session the team also identified established volunteer networks and potential local events for Urban ReLeaf to join. The session was vital to facilitate dialogue between cities, promote knowledge exchange and build partnerships.

Figure 2. Urban ReLeaf work packages and interdependencies

On Day 2 the WP2 breakout sessions focused on tackling a key project objective of *assessing current urban greening policy processes and co-creating solutions that use citizen observations to complement existing data ecosystems and decision-making*. Led by VUB, discussions were centered around understanding the current state and extent of citizen science inclusion in policy processes across the six cities. City-specific interactive Miro boards were used by partners to define pilot goals, map the current state, gaps and opportunities for local citizen engagement and urban greening (Figure 3). In addition, a prioritization exercise was conducted using the Center for Design of Creative Thinking (COCD) methodology to converge ideas into three categories: “How”, “Now” and “Wow”. The “How” ideas are innovative but not yet feasible, the “Now” ideas are easy to implement that are common, and the “Wow” ideas are innovative and also achievable. Ultimately the project will aim to implement as many Wow ideas as possible. Partners started this exercise during the kick-off workshop and then completed it within three weeks. In addition, city partners were introduced to templates to identify and catalog relevant local policies, authorities and stakeholders for anticipated interviews and workshops (D2.1, D2.2).

Figure 3. Miro board for mapping and prioritizing local citizen engagement and greening opportunities

The WP3 breakout sessions targeted the mapping of the Urban ReLeaf data ecosystem. We aimed to catalogue data assets, digital tools, mobile devices, wearables, *in-situ* monitoring systems, and data platforms in the domain of urban greenspace for the six cities. To facilitate this process the team will use methods described within the Open Data Institute (ODI) data landscape playbook and data ethics canvas. Comprehensive data cataloging templates were introduced by WP3 lead ICCS to identify existing data sources and relevant metadata. Each

city partner will continue to complete these templates until the end of March, where these templates will include detailed information on data type, format, interface, accessibility, usability, licenses, and ethical considerations. These templates will contribute to the anticipated city-specific data ecosystem maps (D3.1), which will also draw from insights acquired from WP2.

The final session on Day 2, led by the WP6 lead UNIVDUN, engaged partners in a series of exercises to help define the Urban ReLeaf communication channels, core values and brand design. The session focused on storytelling platforms and building the project's brand 'look and feel', and values to communicate to a multi-stakeholder audience in order to support co-creation activities and impact in city pilots. For the first exercise, partners exchanged stories that they have recently shared with someone. Participants identified a favorite story (i.e. article, film, visualization, report, etc.) that they shared this month along with who, how and why they shared it. Next, the various inputs were clustered to determine insights on the various drivers for sharing a story and also where people share stories (i.e. digital platforms). Additional attention was given to recognize which channels might be successful in reaching marginalized groups. The second brainstorming exercise was designed to build a collection of values associated with Urban ReLeaf in order to narrow it down to 3-4 core values. These inputs will help to build the identity of the project and the approach it takes towards dissemination and communication moving forward. Finally, during the third exercise participants shared various brands and designs that inspire them. Good branding can help people to recognize and connect with Urban ReLeaf. As such, with the contributions from this session, the team will build a compelling brand for Urban ReLeaf and help emphasize its core values and topic by Month 6 (D6.2).

Day 3 of the workshop started with presentations from the coordinators of the sister projects CitiObs and GREENGAGE. This exchange helped to spur synergies and cooperation, and follow-up meetings with the coordinators are planned for late March. Núria Castell and Jan Peters Anders, coordinators of CitiObs and GREENGAGE, both serve on the Urban ReLeaf Expert Advisory Board (EAB). In addition, Gerid Hager is also on the scientific advisory board of GREENGAGE, which will ensure continued collaboration between the sister projects. Day 3 was also dedicated to outlining management/coordination protocols as well as defining action items and assignments. Key elements of the consortium agreement were summarized, namely the operating procedures of the General Assembly (GA) and the Steering Committee (SC). In addition, IIASA introduced the plan for monthly teleconferences with individual city pilots as well as the full consortium. Furthermore, a year 1 roadmap detailing subtasks was initiated at the workshop and then completed later. Due to the structured project workflow, the kick-off workshop prioritized tasks that started in month one, namely within WP1, 2, 3, as well WP6. The key outcomes from the workshop are outlined in Table 3.

Table 3: Outcomes from the kick-off workshop

Outcomes	Related WPs	Dependencies
<p>Project management and coordination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Urban ReLeaf internal exchange platform (MS Teams/Sharepoint) was established to facilitate document sharing, collaboration, archiving and discussion. 	WP1	D1.1

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduced plans for monthly conference calls with full consortium and city pilots Followed-up with partners after the kick-off to schedule monthly conference calls Started the detailed project work plan at the kickoff and completed it afterwards with WP lead inputs (Section 5 and Figure 4) 		
<p>Stakeholder dialogue and inclusive citizen participation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initiated the mapping of current state, gaps and opportunities for citizen engagement and urban greening across pilot cities. Conducted prioritization exercises using Center for Development of Creative Thinking (COCD) How Now Wow matrix to converge ideas across pilot cities Identified key relevant policies Starting building contact list of local authorities and stakeholders Introduced the Participatory Action Research for the development of Policies (PAR4P) methodology to the team for stakeholder workshops 	WP2	D2.1 D2.2
<p>Data ecosystem and technology to bridge citizen-powered and authoritative data ecosystems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduced the Open Data Institute (ODI) data landscape playbook and data ethics canvas for data ecosystem mapping Established a template for initial mapping of existing geospatial data, technologies, and assets Provided preliminary overview of the low-cost temperature/humidity and air quality sensors. 	WP3	D3.1 D3.2 D2.1
<p>Dissemination, exploitation and strategic communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connected with sister projects (CitiObs and Greengage) through remote presentations and further discussions Identification of the Urban ReLeaf core values and branding principles to facilitate project website design and development 	WP6	D6.1 D6.2

5. Year 1 detailed work plan

In addition to the fruitful discussions, the kick-off workshop acted as an important platform to clarify and establish partner roles and responsibilities. Building on the Urban ReLeaf proposal, the team detailed subtasks, namely for WPs 1, 2, 3 and 6, to facilitate clear communication and timelines across the consortium regarding partner roles and responsibilities (Figure 4). This workplan is shared with all partners in the shared Microsoft Teams platform and will act as a living document to be revised as needed to ensure flexibility throughout the project duration.

Figure 4. Urban ReLeaf Gantt chart with detailed tasking for year 1

6. Conclusions

The Urban ReLeaf kick-off workshop brought together the entire consortium to outline next steps in each of the work packages and ensure the coordination of activities. Dialogue and collaborative working sessions resulted in clarity on tasks to be undertaken over the next six months, as well as important linkages across WPs. Management and communication protocols were established to ensure the smooth day-to-day operation of the project.